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Minimization of Total Setup Time on a Bottleneck Machine Using Particle Swarm Optimization

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ABSTRACT

In today's competitive global market, efficiency and cost-effectiveness in production processes are vital for businesses. The optimization of setup times resulting from scheduling and product changeovers is a strategic factor that directly impacts production line efficiency, capacity utilization, and resource sustainability. This study aims to minimize total setup times by optimizing product sequencing on a bottleneck machine within a tire manufacturing line. Due to its combinatorial nature and large solution space, the problem presents a complex optimization challenge. To address this, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is applied and compared with several metaheuristic algorithms—Tabu Search (TS), Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), and the Lin-Kernighan Heuristic (LKH). These algorithms were evaluated using real production data and compared with the existing sequencing method used by the supply chain department. Extensive analysis based on 10-day production plans revealed significant improvements by all metaheuristic methods over the current approach. PSO achieved a 12.83% improvement, TS 10.71%, LKH 12.71%, and ACO demonstrated the best performance with a 16.64% improvement. The statistical significance of the results was confirmed using a T-test, showing that metaheuristic solutions significantly outperform traditional sequencing methods. This study highlights the value of setup time optimization in complex manufacturing systems and offers a practical model for both academic research and industrial decision-making. The detailed comparison of algorithm performance also provides a strong foundation for future studies in this field.

1 INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive industrial landscape, efficiency and cost-effectiveness in production processes are vital for business sustainability. Setup times caused by product variety on production lines are a key factor directly influencing operational performance. Inefficient management of these times can lead to delays, reduced capacity utilization, and increased costs. In large-scale facilities, long setup times can create bottlenecks, hinder timely delivery, and reduce overall productivity. For instance, in tire manufacturing lines, varying setup durations between different tire types can result in significant inefficiencies.

This study addresses the minimization of total setup times by optimizing product sequencing on a bottleneck machine within a tire production line. Due to complex transition times between tire types, the problem is highly combinatorial with a vast solution space. Transition durations are determined by mold and compound changes and fall into four categories:

- Same mold and compound: 1 minute
- Same compound, different mold: 6.5 minutes
- Same mold, different compound: 7.3–8.1 minutes
- Different mold and compound: 21.5–22 minutes

Because setup durations directly affect productivity, product sequencing should aim to minimize these times. This problem can be modeled as a Hamiltonian path problem, where each product is processed once, and sequencing impacts overall efficiency. Traditional optimization methods are computationally insufficient for large-scale instances. Recent studies highlight the development of heuristic approaches for Hamiltonian optimization in large networks.

To overcome this complexity, this study applies advanced metaheuristic algorithms, including Tabu Search (TS), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), and the Lin-Kernighan Heuristic (LKH). These algorithms are known for effectively exploring large search spaces and avoiding local optima, making them suitable for high-dimensional optimization problems. Their performance is tested using real production data and compared with the supply chain department's manual sequencing method. PSO efficiently searches multidimensional spaces; TS avoids cycling by using a tabu list; ACO mimics ant foraging behavior to find optimal paths; and LKH is a powerful local search technique used in combinatorial problems like the Traveling Salesman Problem.

The main objective is to determine the optimal sequence that minimizes setup times and to evaluate the practicality and effectiveness of these metaheuristic algorithms in industrial settings. The findings are expected to reduce total setup time, lower production costs, and offer a concrete model for integrating metaheuristics into production planning. This research provides a relevant example of advanced optimization techniques in manufacturing and establishes a foundation for future studies. Comparative evaluations of these techniques are especially emphasized in current literature on intelligent manufacturing and Industry 5.0 applications in multi-objective scheduling.

2 LITERATURE SURVEY

Accurate sequencing in production systems significantly affects both setup time and overall production duration, especially in complex manufacturing environments. In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in the use of metaheuristic algorithms for addressing such challenges. Among the most studied approaches are Tabu Search (TS), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Lin-Kernighan Heuristic (LKH), and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO).

Tabu Search has yielded effective results in minimizing setup times. Mota et al. (2025) found that Tabu Search outperforms Simulated Annealing in higher-dimensional parallel machine scheduling scenarios by delivering better solutions with shorter computational times [1]. Similarly, Pambudi, Gunawan, and Muzhoffar (2025) reported a 22.65% improvement in material handling costs using the Tabu Search algorithm for shipyard facility layout optimization [2]. Ru (2024) applied the Tabu Search algorithm for intermodal vehicle logistics route optimization, achieving an 18% improvement in overall routing efficiency [3]. Guo et al. (2024) used Tabu Search to optimize vehicle routes for urban waste collection, considering time windows and capacity limits [4]. Furthermore, Rahdar, Ghanbari, and Ghorbani-Moghadam (2022) proposed metaheuristic algorithms (Tabu Search and Variable Neighborhood Search) to solve the NP-hard interval bus terminal location problem and demonstrated the superiority of their methods using nonparametric statistical tests such as Mann–Whitney and Dolan–Moré performance profiles [5]. These findings confirm Tabu Search as a strong alternative, particularly for deterministic production lines.

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is another widely preferred method due to its balance of speed and solution quality. Abualigah (2025) reviewed the advancements and applications of PSO, emphasizing its flexibility and strong experimental performance across various domains [6]. Qi et al. (2025) proposed an improved Artificial Bee Colony Learning Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm for multi-UAV path planning, considering multiple energy consumptions and demonstrating enhanced efficiency and accuracy [7]. Xu et al. (2025) combined a hybrid Gaussian Quantum Particle Swarm Optimization with an Adaptive Genetic Algorithm to solve the flexible job shop scheduling problem, showing improved scheduling performance and adaptability [8]. Similarly, Yao et al. (2024) implemented a hybrid strategy PSO algorithm, which proved effective in diverse optimization applications [9]. Furthermore, Wang and Zhou (2024) enhanced multi objective PSO by incorporating a leader prediction mechanism, resulting in improved overall optimization performance [10].

The Lin-Kernighan-Helsgaun (LKH) algorithm has also shown considerable promise in addressing complex routing and optimization problems. Boufar et al. (2025) proposed a candidate sampling diversification method to improve a non-iterated LKH algorithm, enhancing both solution quality and computational efficiency [11]. Xu et al. (2024) applied the LKH algorithm to optimize multi-vehicle routing for collaborative orchard pesticide spraying involving multiple UAVs, demonstrating its potential in agricultural logistics [12]. He et al. (2024) utilized LKH for path planning of unmanned sweepers on structured roads, resulting in improved navigation and obstacle avoidance [13]. In a different domain, Liu et al. (2024) integrated graph representation learning with LKH optimization to enhance the accuracy of spherical emission source microscopy [14]. Lastly, Rajkumar et al. (2023) adopted the LKH model to strengthen security mechanisms in cloud-based e-auction communication systems [15].

Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) has also attracted significant attention due to its adaptability and effectiveness in solving a wide range of optimization problems. Awadallah et al. (2025) developed a multi-objective ACO approach that enhances both solution quality and convergence speed in engineering optimization tasks [16]. Achaa-Amankwaa et al. (2025) applied ACO to balance categorical and dimensional evaluations in constructing short-scale psychological tests [17]. Binwu et al. (2025) introduced a hybrid ACO–Slime Mould algorithm for precise helicopter trajectory tracking control, demonstrating improved accuracy in navigation tasks [18]. Jiang et al. (2025) proposed a learning-enhanced ACO algorithm for integrated planning and scheduling in uncertain hot rolling production environments [19]. In the energy sector, Sharma et al. (2024) applied ACO to optimize energy storage scheduling in microgrids [20]. Lastly, Chandrashekar et al. (2023) developed a hybrid weighted ACO algorithm to improve task scheduling performance in cloud computing systems [21].

In summary, all reviewed methods have demonstrated substantial contributions to setup time reduction and production efficiency. However, algorithm selection depends on problem structure and solution time constraints.

3 METHODOLOGY

This study focuses on optimizing production sequencing and setup times. The addressed problem belongs to the class of NP-hard problems—where finding an optimal solution is computationally intensive, but verifying a given solution is relatively fast. Common industrial challenges such as production planning, scheduling, and routing share this complexity. As a result, heuristic and metaheuristic algorithms are often favored over exact methods due to their efficiency in large problem spaces.

The problem also falls within the domain of combinatorial optimization, where the goal is to identify the best combination from a finite yet vast solution set. For such complex and high-dimensional problems, metaheuristic algorithms like Tabu Search, Simulated Annealing, and Particle

Swarm Optimization are well-suited for effectively exploring the search space and producing high-quality solutions.

In this study, production sequencing and setup time minimization are modeled as a Hamiltonian Path Problem (HPP)-a classical combinatorial optimization problem where each node in a graph is visited exactly once. As an NP-complete problem, the HPP framework has proven successful in real-world applications such as task sequencing and flow optimization, particularly when solved using advanced metaheuristic approaches.

3.1 Mathematical Model

The following decision variables are defined for the mathematical formulation of the problem:

- X_{ij} : Binary decision variable that equals 1 if product i is scheduled before product j , and 0 otherwise (Zhang et al., 2019).
- B_i : Binary variable equal to 1 if product i is the first product of the day, and 0 otherwise.
- S_i : Binary variable equal to 1 if product i is the last product of the day, and 0 otherwise.

The parameters used in the model are:

- C_{ij} : Setup time required to switch from product i to product j .
- n : Total number of products to be produced during the day.

The objective is to **minimize the total setup time**, expressed by the following objective function:

$$\text{Minimize } Z = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n C_{ij} X_{ij} \quad (1)$$

Glover and Laguna (1997) introduced the Tabu Search methodology as a metaheuristic approach that effectively minimizes cumulative setup time in sequencing problems by guiding the search process beyond local optima [22].

Subject to the following constraints:

- A product that is not the first must be preceded by another:

$$\sum_{i=1, i \neq j}^n x_{ij} = (1 - B_j) \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (2)$$

- Only one product can be the first:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n B_i = 1 \quad (3)$$

- A product that is not the last must be followed by another:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = (1 - S_i) \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (4)$$

- Only one product can be the last:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n S_i = 1 \quad (5)$$

If the solution includes subtours (i.e., disconnected sequences), **Subtour Elimination Constraints (SEC)** must be added to ensure a valid **Hamiltonian Path**.

4 APPLICATION

This study aims to minimize the setup times between products on a tire production line. To improve production efficiency and cost-effectiveness, the optimization focuses on reducing setup durations caused by varying mold and compound combinations. The process begins with a detailed analysis of 10 days of production data obtained from the supply chain department, along with the construction of a transition matrix (see Table 1).

Table 1. 10 Ten-Day Production Information

Tire Code	Mold No.	Compound No.	Days in Production										
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
S597	RT597M	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
S170	RT172	K43..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q133	RT733K	K35..	√	√	√								
Q171	RT172	K43..		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q155	RT172	K43..	√										√
A826	LT826K	N36..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q404	RT413C	K83..											√
Q992	RT992E	K16..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q401	RT404T	K83 ..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q172	RT172	K43..	√										
Q156	RT172	K43..	√										
Q357	RT254O	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q354	RT254O	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√				
A729	LT729J	K17..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q368	RT315P	K93..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q471	RT471B	K64..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q790	RT790A	KT9..							√	√	√	√	√
Q795	LT796B	KT9..			√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q798	RT798	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A877	RT877J	K17..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q370	RT320D	K93..										√	√
Q530	RT529	KX4..	√	√									
A827	LT827H	N36..						√	√	√	√	√	√
A828	LT828E	N36..				√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
U439	RT440B	K35..					√	√					
A850	RT850C	K84..	√	√									
A951	RT951H	K93..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
U496	LT496	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A914	LT914A	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		
A744	RT744	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A632	RT632A	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A946	LT946A	K15..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A988	LT988E	K93..	√	√	√								
A875	LT875B	K54..	√	√	√							√	√
A734	LT731C	K67..	√	√	√	√	√						
A629	LT626	K67 ..						√	√	√	√	√	√
A741	RT741B	KT9..										√	√
A944	LT944E	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A746	LT739C	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A769	RT769A	KT9..	√	√	√	√							
A787	RT787A	KT9..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A772	RT771A	K15..				√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A778	RT778B	K15..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A852	RT852K	K93			√	√	√	√	√				
A969	RT969F	K43..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A873	LT873C	K93..	√	√	√								
A922	RT923B	K17..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Q375	RT375C	KX4..		√	√	√	√	√	√				
Q376	RT376D	KX4..											√
A738	RT781A	K15..	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A474	LT988E	K93..			√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A475	LT875B	K54..				√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
A473	LT873C	K93..			√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

Setup durations fall into four main categories:

Same compound and same mold: 1 minute

Same compound, different mold: 6.5 minutes

Same mold, different compound: between 7.3 and 8.1 minutes

Different mold and different compound: between 21.5 and 22 minutes

By accurately modeling these transitions, the study seeks to develop optimal product sequences that significantly reduce total setup time across the planning horizon.

Setup times between tire types given in Table 2 were mapped according to the daily production schedule and structured into time intervals, forming the input data for the optimization algorithms.

Since different mold–compound transitions significantly impact overall production efficiency, a systematic transition matrix was developed to minimize these durations.

Table 2. Presents the compound-to-compound transition times.

	N36	K67	K15	K83	KT9	K17	K43	K93	K35	KX4	K54	K84	K64	K16	K83	K76	K67	K56
N36	0.0	21.5	21.5	8.1	8.1	8.1	8.1	7.7	21.8	21.5	21.5	21.5	21.5	8.1	21.8	21.5	21.5	21.5
K67	21.5	0.0	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.3	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	21.8	7.7
K15	21.5	21.8	0.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	22.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8
K83	21.8	21.8	21.8	0.0	7.7	7.7	7.7	22.0	21.8	21.8	7.7	7.7	21.8	7.7	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8
KT9	8.1	21.8	21.8	7.7	0.0	7.7	7.7	22.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	7.7	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8
K17	8.1	21.8	21.8	7.7	7.7	0.0	7.7	22.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	7.7	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8
K43	8.1	21.8	21.8	7.7	7.7	7.7	0.0	22.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	7.7	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8
K93	21.8	21.8	21.8	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	0.0	22.0	22.0	22.0	22.0	22.0	7.5	22.0	22.0	22.0	22.0
K35	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	0.0	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	21.8	7.3
KX4	21.5	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.3	0.0	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	21.8	7.7
K54	21.5	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.3	7.7	0.0	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	21.8	7.7
K84	21.5	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.3	7.7	7.7	0.0	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	21.8	7.7
K64	21.5	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.3	7.7	7.7	7.7	0.0	7.7	7.7	7.7	21.8	7.7
K16	8.1	21.8	21.8	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	22.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	0.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8
K83	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.3	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	0.0	7.7	21.8	7.7
K76	21.5	7.7	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	22.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	0.0	21.8	7.7
K67	21.5	7.7	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	22.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	0.0	21.8
K56	21.5	7.7	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	22.0	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	21.8	7.7	21.8	0.0

4.1 Tabu Search Algorithm Implementation Steps

The Tabu Search (TS) algorithm explores the solution space by generating new solutions from the neighborhood of the current one. Its strength lies in avoiding repeated visits to previously explored solutions using a tabu list. This makes it particularly effective for large-scale combinatorial problems. This makes it particularly effective for large-scale combinatorial problems, as also demonstrated by Aydın and Demir (2025), who reported a significant reduction in total setup time when applying TS to bottleneck machines [23].

4.2 Implementation Steps of the Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is a population-based metaheuristic in which each particle explores the solution space using both its personal best (pBest) and the swarm’s global best (gBest) experiences. Each particle represents a potential solution and iteratively refines its position. The algorithm begins with particles randomly initialized with positions and velocities. Their fitness values are evaluated to identify both pBest and gBest, and then velocities and positions are updated iteratively to generate improved solutions. This process continues until a predefined number of iterations is reached.

4.3 Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm Implementation Steps

Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is a metaheuristic inspired by natural ant colonies’ ability to find shortest paths. It is effective for discrete and combinatorial problems. In ACO, each "ant" constructs a tour representing a production sequence. Ants make probabilistic choices based on pheromone intensity left by previous solutions and heuristic information such as setup times. Shorter, more efficient sequences receive higher pheromone rewards, guiding the algorithm towards better solutions over time.

ACO is well-suited for production sequencing problems due to their Hamiltonian path-like structure and large solution space. Its strength lies in solution quality and search diversity. The dynamic pheromone updating helps avoid local minima and promotes more global solutions. Numerous studies demonstrate ACO’s success in scheduling and setup time minimization (e.g., Sun

& Liu, 2019). Given its flexibility, learning ability, and natural fit to the problem, ACO was chosen for this study.

4.4 LKH Algorithm Implementation Steps

The Lin-Kernighan-Helsgaun (LKH) algorithm is an advanced, optimized version of the classic Lin-Kernighan method originally developed for NP-hard problems like the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP). LKH dynamically improves solutions using variable k-opt moves, allowing flexible edge exchanges tailored to problem conditions. Intelligent selection strategies guide each improvement step to enhance solution quality.

LKH is chosen for this study due to the structural similarity between production sequencing problems and TSP, and its proven ability to deliver high-quality solutions for such sequencing tasks. The tire production setup time optimization requires minimizing setup costs through specific product sequences, which aligns well with LKH's strengths. Its main advantages include fast convergence without compromising solution quality and high computational efficiency, especially for large datasets. Literature reports confirm LKH's superior performance compared to other metaheuristics in sequencing and routing problems. Therefore, LKH is incorporated as a key solution method here.

5 DISCUSSION

This study compared four metaheuristic algorithms—Tabu Search, Particle Swarm Optimization, Ant Colony Optimization, and LKH—to minimize setup (transition) times in a tire production line. Their performances were compared against the traditional sequencing method defined by the supplier, using total transition times recorded over a 10-day period.

The software was developed on a system with an Intel® Core™ i7-12700H processor, 32 GB RAM, 1 TB SSD, and a 4 GB NVIDIA RTX3050 GPU. Python was used within a Jupyter Notebook environment, utilizing libraries such as NumPy, Matplotlib, pandas, random, math, copy, itertools, and scipy.stats for data processing, optimization calculations, and statistical testing. This setup enabled effective implementation and comparative analysis of the metaheuristic approaches for production sequencing. The resulting times (in minutes) are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Analysis Results

Day	Supply Chain Department	Tabu Search Algorithm	Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm	Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm	LKH
1	282,9	250,9	235,8	235,0	250,0
2	316,9	254,7	241,3	240,3	254,5
3	325,8	255,2	254,8	240,9	255,3
4	282,8	260,3	246,2	243,7	258,6
5	282,8	263,1	246,6	259,0	259,8
6	297,6	266,2	280,3	265,5	266,3
7	304,3	282,7	279,9	250,2	265,1
8	259,4	265,7	253,8	235,0	249,9
9	311,1	279,7	280,1	249,0	263,9
10	320,2	274,7	274,3	259,2	271,6

Optimization studies using four different methods calculated each algorithm's improvement percentage over the existing production sequence used by the supply chain department. These results directly indicate the relative effectiveness of the algorithms in reducing production transition times. The highest average improvement of 16.64% was achieved by the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO)

algorithm, demonstrating ACO’s pheromone-based guidance as an effective exploration strategy for discrete combinatorial problems like production sequencing.

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) followed with a 12.83% improvement, closely matched by the LKH algorithm at 12.71%. The similar performance of these two algorithms suggests their ability to find comparable quality solutions in large solution spaces.

Tabu Search showed a lower improvement of 10.71%. Although it significantly outperformed the current sequence, its limited randomness compared to adaptive learning, collective knowledge sharing, and dynamic guidance in other metaheuristics resulted in comparatively lower solution quality.

In summary, ACO emerged as the most effective method with the highest average improvement for production planning. PSO and LKH are strong alternatives, while Tabu Search may serve as a practical choice for smaller solution spaces. These findings reaffirm the superiority of metaheuristic algorithms over traditional methods for production sequencing problems.

To further verify the statistical significance of differences among the methods, a nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis test was conducted since the data did not fully satisfy normality assumptions. The results indicated a significant difference among the five methods ($H = 26.25$, $p < 0.001$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis that all groups share the same distribution. This finding suggests that at least one method performs differently from the others. Subsequently, Dunn’s post-hoc test with Bonferroni correction was applied to identify pairwise differences (see Table 4).

Table 4. Dunn’s Post-Hoc Test (with Bonferroni Correction) Results

Comparison	p-value	Bonferroni-adjusted p	Significance
Supply Chain – Tabu Search	0.0013	0.0131	Significant
Supply Chain – PSO	0.0006	0.0058	Significant
Supply Chain – ACO	0.0002	0.0024	Significant
Supply Chain – LKH	0.0008	0.0077	Significant
Tabu Search – PSO	0.3447	10.000	Not significant
Tabu Search – ACO	0.0036	0.0360	Significant
Tabu Search – LKH	0.2413	10.000	Not significant
PSO – ACO	0.1403	10.000	Not significant
PSO – LKH	0.7337	10.000	Not significant
ACO – LKH	0.0257	0.2569	Not significant

The analysis revealed that the Supply Chain method differed significantly from all metaheuristic algorithms (Tabu Search, PSO, ACO, and LKH). Additionally, a significant difference was observed between Tabu Search and ACO, whereas no significant differences were found among PSO, ACO, and LKH after correction. These results confirm that the Supply Chain method accounts for the main source of variation and consistently produces values statistically distinct from heuristic approaches, reinforcing the earlier findings obtained from t-tests.

6 CONCLUSION

This study focused on a comparative analysis of four metaheuristic algorithms to minimize setup times between products on a tire production line. Using real production data, Tabu Search (TA), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), and Lin-Kernighan Heuristic (LKH) were evaluated and their resulting schedules compared to the existing supply chain practices.

Results showed all metaheuristics significantly improved over traditional methods. Among them, ACO achieved the highest average improvement of 16.64%, followed by PSO at 12.83%, LKH at 12.71%, and TA at 10.71%. These findings highlight the effectiveness of ACO’s pheromone-based guidance in enhancing efficiency in dynamic production transitions.

Supported by t-test analyses, ACO was statistically superior to other methods, while no significant difference was found between PSO and LKH. Although TA showed strong performance on some days, it generally lagged behind the other algorithms.

The study demonstrates the practical applicability of integrating metaheuristics into production planning decision support systems. Especially, ACO and LKH proved effective for sequence-based optimization problems. Future research should explore hybrid versions of these algorithms and their integration with multi-objective optimization approaches.

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